

Educational system in Slovenia

Slovenian pre-tertiary education consist of compulsory 9-year basic education, which is provided within elementary school and 3-4 year secondary education (Figure 1). Nine years of elementary school is formally divided into triads, however, from the point of view of the teachers who teach there, we distinguish 5 years of class-level and 4 years of subject-level. The class-level (1 – 5 class) is taught by primary teachers. They are teaching all the subjects (e.g. math, mother tongue, science, music education ...), which means, primary teacher education covers a wide range of areas. While the subject-level (6 – 9 class), so called lower secondary school level, and is taught by subject teachers. They are mostly teaching two subjects. Subject teachers are teaching in secondary education, as well.

Figure 1: Pre-tertiary education in Slovenia

Prospective teacher education in Slovenia

To become a primary or subject teacher, a candidate should have finished a Master degree (300 ECTS), including at least 60 ECTS of educational subjects and teaching practice, which takes at least 5 years of study. Because faculties are autonomous in organization of the study programmes various models exists (3+2, 4+1, 0+5).

Subject teacher study programmes are offering two options of study: one-stream study (one-subject teacher, have a possibility to teach also on the secondary schools, which are having a matriculation programmes), and two-stream study (two-subject teachers can teach on lower secondary schools and upper secondary schools, with no matriculation programmes).

After one year of apprenticeship in teaching, the candidate can approach for the state exam, a professional exam, which allows a candidate to obtain a lifelong teaching license.